

APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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Annotation

The article highlights the advantages of using the basic principles and rules of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process of general education schools. Information about the role of information technology in conducting modern education is presented.

Key words : information technology, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

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V state vydeleny preimushchestva ospolzovaniya osnovnykh principov i pravil innovatsionnykh pedagogicheskikh technologi v obrazovatelnom procese obshcheobrazovatelnoy school. Predstavlena information about the role of information technology in modern implementation.

Key words: information technology, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

Abstract

The article highlights the advantages of using the main principles and rules of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process of general education schools. Information about the role of information technologies in conducting modern education is presented.

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Introduction

The introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process is based on certain laws and principles. Principle is derived from the Latin word "princepium", which means "basic", "initial condition", "guiding idea", "generalized requirement". Pedagogical technology principles are general standards and requirements to be followed in order to achieve high results in the implementation of the planned educational process . When determining them, the following circumstances are taken into account:

1. The goal of education that meets the requirements of the existing society;
2. Objective laws of the didactic process;
3. Conditions that implement the educational process;

Main Part

The principle of integrity of pedagogical technology - this principle requires taking into account that all elements of the pedagogical system are under mutual influence and interdependence when creating a technology project. That is, the strict determination of the educational goal (why? and why?), the content of the educational process (what?), the selection of organizational forms (how?), teaching methods and tools (with what?) and should help to choose, as well as allow to determine the effectiveness of the didactic process depending on the teacher's skill level.

denies that the first of the elements that make up the pedagogical technology should be updated or changed, and the rest should not be touched or rebuilt. For example, it is impossible to change the purpose of education and leave its content or teaching process in the same way . Today, profound changes and reforms are being implemented in the Republic's education system:

- First of all, the goal of education has been updated - it is necessary to form a free-thinking citizen, a well-rounded human personality.
- Secondly, this social order, in turn, causes a radical restructuring of the educational content, the creation of new textbooks and programs.
- Thirdly, the new content of education requires tools that speed up the process of delivering information to teachers within a certain time frame.

Pedagogical technologies envisage the planning of the educational process in advance and the implementation of this project in the classroom. Therefore, an important principle of pedagogical technology is the principle of planning the future educational process in advance. This, of course, requires creative activity from the teacher. The designed technology should be introduced within the time allotted to the subject of the lesson.

Study time is an important indicator in the pre-construction of pedagogical technology, and the teacher must take it into account. It is very important that the planned didactic process corresponds to the students' learning level and is understandable to everyone. Only then will the final result be achieved. The guarantee of the final result is another important principle of pedagogical technology . This concept is actually relative in nature, because it is natural that after the implementation of the structured technology, there will be certain results - students will master the learning material at different levels.

Another important principle of pedagogical technology is the principle of completeness. The student's learning quality is determined by his learning coefficient. In the educational institutions of our country, the quality of learning

of pupils (students) - if the coefficient of learning is equal to or more than 0.55, that is, if 55% of the educational material is learned, " is considered "satisfactory". In our opinion, this indicator is sufficient for the initial stages of reforming the education system.

One of the principles of pedagogical technology is the principle of flexibility. This principle somewhat expands the fields of application of pedagogical technologies. The technology designed for this or that topic should be flexible at least within the boundaries of disciplines . The teacher will have the opportunity to replace or redesign the structure of the didactic process on the subjects of the subject in accordance with the diagnostic purpose, with little effort and time spent. Analyzing the results of scientific research by V.P.Bespalko, B.Skinner, NDNikandrov, NFTalizina, BLFerberman and others, the following principles of pedagogical technology can be distinguished :

1. Creating a strict sequence of the system of devices that control students' cognitive activity. Controlling devices control students' cognitive activity only when pre-programmed by a pedagogue or methodologist (methodologist). Pedagogical activity is necessary to manage the situations that arise in the educational process, but are not pre-programmed. Today, creating a fully programmed e-book is currently ineffective. In managing students' cognitive activities, it is necessary for the student to design effective use of machine-assisted (automatic) and their joint and self-management types.

Organization of the management of the educational process in each part of the students' cognitive activity according to a closed cycle. In addition to direct information transfer to students, receiving information from them - feedback communication is taken into account. It is known from cybernetics that for the normal functioning of the control system, a correct and reversible connection must be established between the machine and the object (student). Both the teacher and the student are equally important in feedback . For the student to master the educational material, and for the teacher to analyze the mistakes made and make appropriate corrections to the pedagogical process. Feedback, which is necessary for the learner to independently make appropriate adjustments to his work, is called feedback. Thanks to the internal feedback, the student will have the opportunity to consciously master his knowledge and skills. In this case, no explanations, advices, referrals, etc. are allowed. It is possible to control the learning process in a cyclical manner only if external feedback is established by the teacher.

of separate steps in the transmission of educational materials, revealing its

essence . Fulfillment of these requirements ensures that the program material is comprehensible to all. Each step covers the following three interrelated parts of training content : information, feedback operation and control. The sequence of educational steps forms the basis of pedagogical technology. Students' activities in the program (each educational step) are highly individualized.

4. The fourth principle is called the individual image of mastery. Adherence to this principle ensures that all students (albeit at different times) fully master the learning material. In this case, it is necessary to choose the educational materials that are most suitable for each student's mental (perception, attention, thinking) development and determine the learning trajectory that suits him. will

5. Use of special technical devices in the educational process. A special technical device is a technical means that implements each learning step (information, operation, feedback, control).

Conclusion

The above principles determine the specific characteristics of pedagogical technology as a didactic system. However, they do not reflect all aspects related to the organization of the educational process.

Pedagogical technology, as a special case, uses traditional teaching and all the principles of didactics (consciousness and activity, demonstrability, connection of theory with practice, coherence in teaching, comprehensibility of teaching and thoroughness of knowledge). Pedagogical technology principles and general didactic principles complement and enrich each other.

List Of References : (References):

1. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
2. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
3. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
4. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
5. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).

6. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
7. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). FIZIKA FANINI O 'RGANISHNING YUQORI DARAJADAGI STRATEGIYALAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 152-156.
8. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). TA'LIM SOHASIDA FIZIKANING SAN'AT BILAN ALOQALARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 144-147.
9. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 162-167.
10. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(27), 9-20.
11. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(27), 9-20.
12. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(21), 143-150.
13. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 77-87.
14. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 360-365.
15. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 137-141.
16. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 135-138.
17. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. *International journal of sciearchers*, 2(2), 101-103.
18. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
19. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 102-110.

20. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
21. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.
22. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 115-121.
23. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.
24. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420-424.
25. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425-429.
26. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525-532.
27. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
28. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING "PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
29. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.
30. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.
31. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
32. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.
33. Muxayyo Muxtor qizi Sharopova. (2023). INTRODUCING "PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.

34. Muxayyo Muxtor qizi Sharopova. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
35. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
36. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
37. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
38. Quvvatov, B. U. o'g'li . (2023). ALEXNET - TASVIRLARNI TASNIFLASH UCHUN KONVOLYUTSION NEYRON TARMOQ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 77-90.
39. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
40. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
41. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
42. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
43. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 134-139.
44. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
45. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
46. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
47. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.

48. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA*, 1(6), 128-132.
49. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(12), 781-787.
50. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 274-280.
51. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(13), 120-128.
52. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(21), 171-177.
53. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(12), 99-109.
54. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(13), 113-120.
55. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 305-309.
56. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TO'G'RI MASALALAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 375-382.
57. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 66-76.
58. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 383-390.
59. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 391-399.
60. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
61. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(10), 13-23.

62. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
63. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
64. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
65. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
66. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG-LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
67. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
68. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
69. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
70. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
71. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.
72. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
73. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
74. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference

Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.

75. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. Science and Education, 3(6), 495-507.
76. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. Молодой ученый, (23), 105-106.
77. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
78. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
79. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
80. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.
81. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 35-39.
82. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Hamidov, E. (2023). YADRO ENERGIYASINING XOSSA VA XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182-186.
83. IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION
84. SZ Jurakulov, O Nurboyev - GOLDEN BRAIN, 2023